

Perceived Influence of Utilisation of Library Information Resources on Academic Performance of Postgraduates in Universities in Benue State

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Abstract

This study investigated the perceived influence of library information resources on the academic performance of postgraduate students at universities in Benue State, Nigeria. Academic libraries serve as critical hubs for teaching, learning, and research, offering both physical and digital resources essential for advanced scholarly work. Guided by a descriptive survey design, data were collected from 368 postgraduate students across Joseph Sarwuan Tarka University, Benue State University, and the University of Mkar using a structured questionnaire. Descriptive statistics and Chi-square tests were used to analyse responses on the types of library resources available, the extent of their use, perceived impact on academic performance, and the challenges faced by students. Findings revealed that research journals and online databases were the most utilised resources, while e-books, theses, and reference materials were less frequently accessed. Postgraduate students perceived library resources as having a strong positive influence on academic performance, particularly in enhancing access to relevant materials, supporting academic writing, improving critical thinking, and facilitating time management and effective presentations. However, challenges such as limited digital access, inadequate internet connectivity, insufficient training, outdated materials, and constrained library infrastructure were significant barriers to optimal utilisation. The study concludes that effective engagement with library resources is essential for improving postgraduate research quality and scholarly productivity. Recommendations include enhancing digital infrastructure, expanding awareness and training programmes, improving resource availability, and strengthening library facilities to support postgraduate learning and research.

Keywords: Library Information Resources, Utilisation, Academic Performance, Postgraduates, Universities

Introduction

University libraries play a strategic role in postgraduate education by supporting teaching, learning, and advanced research. As intellectual centres, they provide access to a wide range of scholarly resources and foster both independent inquiry and collaborative learning. Shinde (2018) notes that the effectiveness of university libraries depends not only on the availability of resources but also on users' awareness and understanding of library facilities and services. The integration of digital technologies has further expanded library services beyond physical boundaries, enabling postgraduate students to access electronic databases, journals, and other online resources remotely. In addition to their collections, academic libraries

offer specialised services such as reference assistance, research consultations, and information literacy training, all designed to meet the increasingly complex academic demands of postgraduate programmes. These evolving services and resources therefore emphasise the need to clearly understand the nature and scope of the library information resources available to postgraduate students.

Library information resources are central to academic library services and include both print and electronic materials. According to Owusi and Mundi (2021), print resources such as textbooks, journals, reference works, and these remain vital for foundational knowledge, while functional ICT facilities and digital resources significantly enhance access to current and diverse information. Digital resources, including e-books, electronic journals, databases, and multimedia materials, facilitate timely access to specialised scholarly content and promote flexible learning. Olise (2021) further explains that the effective organisation and accessibility of these resources are critical to supporting research productivity within universities. The breadth and accessibility of library resources enable postgraduate students to engage with recent and relevant research in their respective disciplines. However, this increased availability of information makes effective utilisation a key determinant of academic success.

Postgraduate students enrolled in master's, doctoral, and other advanced academic programmes are required to undertake intensive, independent, and specialised research. Their academic responsibilities demand advanced critical thinking, problem-solving, and the ability to synthesise complex information from multiple sources. Ugah (2020) observes that the utilisation of library resources is strongly influenced by how well these resources are organised and made accessible to users, particularly through cataloguing and classification practices. Effective utilisation, therefore, goes beyond mere access to materials to include the ability to navigate digital systems, conduct strategic searches, and manage academic citations appropriately. To support these demands, libraries provide workshops, tutorials, and personalised research assistance to strengthen students' information literacy skills. The extent to which postgraduate students benefit from these supports ultimately reflects in their academic performance.

Academic performance at the postgraduate level is commonly assessed through grades, research quality, and the successful completion of scholarly outputs such as theses and dissertations. Ogunbodede and Oribhabor (2022) note that the use of digital and library resources significantly influences students' academic performance by enhancing learning efficiency and research outcomes. High academic performance is characterised by originality, analytical depth, and methodological rigour, all of which depend heavily on access to quality library resources and effective support services. This relationship is particularly significant in Benue State, where universities often contend with limited resources and infrastructural constraints. Understanding how the use of library information resources influences postgraduate academic performance in this context is therefore essential for improving library services, strengthening research productivity, and enhancing overall academic success in the region.

Statement of the Problem

Postgraduate education depends heavily on the effective use of library information resources to support advanced research and the production of original scholarly work. Although these resources are designed to enhance independent inquiry and improve academic performance, evidence from universities in Benue State indicates that many postgraduate students do not make optimal use of them. Challenges such as inadequate digital infrastructure, limited access to current resources, insufficient information literacy skills, and poor awareness of available library services often prevent students from fully engaging with these materials, thereby constraining the quality of their research and academic outputs.

The consequences of this underutilisation are significant for both students and institutions. For students, postgraduate students may struggle to produce high-quality theses and dissertations, which can undermine

their academic success. For institutions, weak engagement with library resources can diminish research quality and harm universities' scholarly reputations in Benue State. Addressing this problem is therefore essential, as understanding how library resource utilisation influences academic performance will provide insights needed to improve postgraduate education, strengthen research productivity, and enhance overall academic outcomes in the region.

Objectives

The primary objective of this study is to investigate the perceived influence of library information resources on the academic performance of postgraduates at universities in Benue State, Nigeria. Specifically, the study seeks to:

1. Find out the types of library information resources available to be utilised by postgraduate students in Universities in Benue State, Nigeria
2. Ascertain the extent to which library information resources are utilised among postgraduate students in universities in Benue State, Nigeria
3. Ascertain the perceived influence of utilising library information resources on the academic performance of Postgraduate students in universities in Benue State, Nigeria
4. Find out the challenges affecting the utilisation of library information resources by Postgraduate students in universities in Benue State, Nigeria

Literature Review

This section will consist of the following subheadings: Theoretical Framework, Conceptual Framework, Review of Related Empirical Studies and Summary of Literature Reviewed

Theoretical Framework

The Shannon and Weaver Information Theory (1947) explains communication as a process in which information is transmitted from a sender to a receiver through a channel, with an emphasis on minimising noise that can distort the message. The model highlights key components such as the information source, message, transmitter, channel, receiver, and destination, stressing that effective communication depends on accurate encoding, transmission, and decoding of information.

Applied to this study, the theory illustrates how universities transmit academic information to postgraduate students through library information resources. Libraries serve as the channel through which scholarly content is accessed, interpreted, and applied for academic purposes. Effective use of these resources ensures smooth information flow and supports academic performance, while challenges such as poor access, inadequate resources, or limited user skills constitute “noise” that can disrupt information transfer. Thus, the theory provides a clear framework for understanding how efficient use of library resources influences postgraduate students' academic outcomes.

Conceptual Framework

The concepts below will be discussed under the conceptual framework of this study:

Library Information Resources

Library information resources are fundamental to the effective functioning of academic libraries and to achieving teaching, learning, and research objectives within universities. Owusi and Mundi (2021) explain

that these resources include both print and electronic materials that provide access to reliable, current information across academic disciplines. With the advancement of digital technologies, Shinde (2018) observes that academic libraries have expanded beyond traditional print collections to include electronic resources such as e-books, online databases, and other digital platforms that enable flexible and remote access to scholarly information. Similarly, Olise (2021) notes that the availability and proper organisation of both physical and digital resources ensure that academic communities can access credible, up-to-date materials necessary for effective research and learning. In particular, electronic resources have become increasingly indispensable, as Ugah (2020) points out that well-organised and accessible information systems enhance efficient information retrieval and support high-quality academic work among university users.

Despite the growing availability of diverse library resources, challenges with access and effective use persist, particularly among postgraduate students. Ahmed and Ajili (2015) note that inadequate access to electronic information resources, including limited internet connectivity and insufficient devices, continues to hinder effective engagement with library materials. In addition, Nzewi and Kakulu (2022) observe that the increasing volume of digital information can overwhelm students, making it difficult to identify relevant and authoritative sources. To mitigate these challenges, Arumuru and David (2024) explain that academic libraries increasingly provide training programmes, workshops, and individualised research support to strengthen information literacy and research competencies. These interventions are especially critical for postgraduate students, as they enhance their capacity to access, evaluate, and apply information effectively, thereby improving academic performance and research outcomes.

Utilisation

Utilisation in higher education goes beyond mere access to library resources and focuses on how effectively students and researchers engage with them to achieve meaningful academic outcomes. Ekong and Ogunode (2022) explain that library resources and services form the backbone of teaching, learning, and research activities, and that their effective utilisation significantly influences postgraduate students' research output and academic success. These resources include traditional print materials, as well as digital resources such as e-books, online databases, and multimedia content. In the same vein, Olise (2021) notes that effective utilisation of library resources enables students to deepen their knowledge, complete academic tasks efficiently, conduct quality research, and meet the rigorous demands of postgraduate programmes, making utilisation a critical determinant of academic achievement.

Awareness, accessibility, and user competencies are key determinants of resource utilisation among students. Shinde (2018) observes that limited awareness of available library resources often leads to underutilisation, particularly among postgraduate students who require specialised information. To address this issue, Arumuru and David (2024) highlight the importance of library orientations, workshops, and training programmes in equipping users with the skills to access and use both print and electronic resources effectively. However, challenges such as poor internet connectivity, limited digital infrastructure, and information overload persist, as noted by Lawal and Kannan (2021). Consequently, academic libraries provide information literacy training and personalised research support to help students navigate databases, evaluate sources, and manage information efficiently, which is especially vital for postgraduate students engaged in advanced research and thesis writing.

Academic Performance

Academic performance is the extent to which students achieve the learning objectives and academic standards set by their institutions. It reflects the acquisition of knowledge, the development of intellectual skills, and the ability to demonstrate understanding through assessments, research outputs, and other

scholarly activities. Ogunbodede and Oribhabor (2022) describe academic performance as a key indicator of educational effectiveness, emphasising its relationship with students' use of digital and library resources. In higher education, academic performance extends beyond examination results to include the quality of research, analytical depth, and mastery of specialised knowledge required at the postgraduate level.

Beyond individual achievement, academic performance has broader institutional and societal significance. Ekpang and Idhalama (2024) explain that strong academic performance contributes to institutional reputation, research productivity, and the development of skilled human capital. Effective academic performance enhances postgraduate students' career prospects and supports national development by producing knowledgeable, research-oriented graduates. In this sense, academic performance serves not only as a measure of personal success but also as a foundation for educational advancement and socio-economic progress.

Postgraduates

Postgraduates are students who have completed undergraduate study and are enrolled in advanced academic programmes, such as master's and doctoral degrees. These programmes are designed to develop advanced intellectual, analytical, and research skills necessary to address complex academic and societal challenges. Adamu and Maidabino (2020) explain that postgraduate education emphasises higher-level learning, research specialisation, and the application of theoretical knowledge to practical and scholarly problems. Similarly, Okafor (2020) views postgraduate education as a critical stage of academic development that prepares individuals for professional, academic, and research-oriented careers.

A defining feature of postgraduate study is its strong emphasis on independent research and close supervision. Adamu and Maidabino (2020) note that postgraduate success largely depends on effective supervision, adherence to academic guidelines, and sustained engagement in research. Through proposal development, data collection, analysis, and thesis or dissertation defence, postgraduate students are trained to contribute original knowledge to their disciplines, positioning them as key stakeholders in academic research and innovation.

Universities

Universities are central institutions of higher learning, responsible for teaching, research, and community service. They provide structured academic environments in which students and researchers engage with knowledge, develop critical skills, and generate new ideas. Creswell and Creswell (2018) note that universities serve as platforms for systematic inquiry and knowledge production, supporting both theoretical and applied research. Through access to qualified faculty, academic resources, and research opportunities, universities play a crucial role in shaping individual development and societal advancement.

In the contemporary academic environment, universities increasingly integrate digital technologies and electronic resources to support learning and research. Mozeh and Ubwa (2017) highlight that access to electronic databases, e-journals, and online platforms has transformed how students and faculty engage with information and conduct research. Despite persistent challenges, including inadequate infrastructure and unequal access to technology, Okpa, Asibi, and Eruvwe (2022) argue that universities remain indispensable, continually adapting to emerging trends and providing the resources necessary for academic achievement, research productivity, and lifelong learning.

Review of Related Studies

The study investigated the utilisation of university libraries and its effect on the academic achievement of undergraduates in selected university libraries in South-South, Nigeria. A descriptive survey method was adopted for the study. The study population consisted of 300 undergraduates from the university under study. A total of 300 copies of the questionnaire were distributed, and 243 were retrieved. Descriptive statistics, including the mean and percentage, were used, with a mean score of 2.5 and above and a percentage score of 50% considered acceptable. The study revealed that learning, research, and exam preparation are benefits of utilising university libraries. Factors impeding the utilisation of the library include obsolete books, poor infrastructure, inadequate orientation to library use, and erratic power supply. Strategies to improve the utilisation of the library to aid academic achievement include providing current books, improving infrastructure, ensuring a constant power supply, and offering library orientation for undergraduates. Both the present and previous studies on the utilisation of library resources and their effect on academic achievement share a common descriptive survey method, focusing on the relationship between library usage and academic performance. While both studies use a structured questionnaire and descriptive statistics to analyse data, they differ in key aspects. The present study targets postgraduate students in Benue State, while the previous study focuses on undergraduate students in South-South Nigeria, with a larger sample size in the present study (368 postgraduates vs. 300 undergraduates). The studies also differ in their focus on regional and academic needs, with the previous study identifying barriers such as outdated resources and infrastructure issues that may affect undergraduates differently from postgraduates. The present study seeks to fill the gap in understanding how postgraduate students use library resources and how this impacts their academic performance, addressing specific challenges that were not fully explored in earlier research.

Olajide and Adio (2017) surveyed the utilisation of resources at the Federal University Oye-Ekiti (FUOYE) Library, Ekiti State, Nigeria. The study employed a descriptive survey design, and the instrument used was a structured questionnaire administered to students at the university. The sample comprised 400 targeted undergraduate students, to whom four hundred copies of the questionnaire were distributed across the four faculties of the university, while three hundred and eighty-four (384) copies were returned and found usable/fit for analysis, representing a response rate of 96%. The study revealed that erratic power supply, inadequate functional resources, insufficient reading space, and a lack of physical facilities, such as toilets, are major problems preventing students from effectively utilising the library's resources to meet their information needs. Both the present and previous studies share a similar research design, using a descriptive survey method with structured questionnaires to investigate the impact of library resource utilisation on academic performance among university students. The studies analyse data using descriptive statistics and focus on identifying factors influencing library use, but they differ in target groups, locations, and focus. The present study examines postgraduate students in Benue State, whereas the previous study examines undergraduates at the Federal University Oye-Ekiti. The geographic and infrastructural differences between these locations may affect library usage patterns. The present study specifically explores how library resource utilisation impacts postgraduate academic performance, a focus not addressed in the previous study, which mainly identifies challenges such as inadequate facilities and power issues. By targeting postgraduates, the present study aims to fill gaps left by previous research, providing insights into how specialised library resources and infrastructure affect their academic outcomes, thereby offering a more nuanced understanding of library usage across different academic levels.

Effiom, Amuchi, Ojedor, Ebuka, and Ubi (2023) examined the impact of information and communication technology (ICT) use on students' academic performance, with particular reference to the University of

Nigeria, Nsukka. A total population of 500 students was sampled using a simple random technique. Data for this study were collected using a well-structured questionnaire. The collected data were analysed using descriptive statistics, such as simple tables and percentages, while the formulated hypotheses were tested using the Pearson Product-Moment Correlation Analysis. The results showed that internet use has led to a significant improvement in students' academic performance at the University of Nigeria, Nsukka. The results also showed that e-learning is significantly related to students' academic performance at the University of Nigeria, Nsukka. However, the results showed that students' use of Facebook is not significantly related to their academic performance. Both the present and previous studies share key similarities, including a descriptive survey research design, structured questionnaires for data collection, and the use of descriptive statistics to analyse the impact of resource utilisation on academic performance. Both studies also test hypotheses, though they use different statistical methods: Chi-square (χ^2) in the present study and Pearson Product-Moment Correlation in the previous one. The studies differ in focus, as the present study investigates the use of library resources and their effect on the academic performance of postgraduate students in Benue State, Nigeria, while the previous study examines the impact of ICT tools, such as the internet and e-learning, on undergraduate students at the University of Nigeria, Nsukka. The target groups also vary, with the present study focusing on postgraduate students, whose academic needs are more advanced, while the previous study examines undergraduates. Additionally, the sample sizes differ (368 postgraduates vs. 500 undergraduates), and the studies explore different types of resources. The present study aims to address gaps left by the previous study, particularly by investigating the specific influence of library resources on postgraduate students' academic outcomes and by considering factors such as library infrastructure, which were not explored in the previous study. In summary, while both studies examine the impact of resource utilisation on academic performance, the present study provides new insights into library usage among postgraduate students, addressing areas not covered by the previous study.

Arumuru and David (2024) studied the impact of instructional resources on academic achievement among Library and Information Science postgraduates in Nigeria. A survey of 185 postgraduate students from multiple universities used a self-structured questionnaire to assess the availability and perceived use of instructional resources. The findings highlight essential instructional resources for effective teaching, emphasising their role in facilitating global connectivity, self-paced learning, and practical skill development. However, the study identifies a concerning trend of low overall availability of instructional resources, despite certain resources, such as ICT facilities and reference materials, being moderately accessible. Moreover, a positive correlation between resource availability and academic performance suggests that a well-equipped learning environment significantly influences student success. Both studies used a descriptive survey research design, employing structured questionnaires to assess how resource utilisation affects postgraduate students' academic performance. The present study focuses specifically on library information resources in Benue State, Nigeria, whereas the previous study examines the impact of instructional resources, including ICT facilities, on Library and Information Science postgraduate students across Nigeria. Both studies aim to explore how access to academic resources influences academic achievement, but the present study centres on library materials such as books and journals, while the previous study addresses a broader range of instructional resources. The present study involves a larger population of 9,200 postgraduate students across multiple universities in Benue State, whereas the previous study has a smaller sample size of 185 students. A key difference is that the previous study highlights the general availability of resources and their correlation with academic success, while the present study focuses on the perceived influence of library resource usage on academic performance, exploring disciplinary differences and intangible factors such as library services. The present study fills

gaps left by the previous research, offering a broader geographic scope, a specific focus on library resources, and an investigation of students' perceptions of resource utilisation.

Ajiboye, Bokoh, Bello, and Idowu (2023) evaluated the influence of library resources and services on research activities among postgraduate students at Southwest Federal Universities in Nigeria. A research design was adopted for the survey. However, a multi-stage sampling procedure was applied to select 378 respondents for the study. Data were assembled using a designed questionnaire on library resources and services that influence postgraduate research activities. Standard deviation, mean, frequency counts and percentages were used to analyse the data. Results reveal that textbooks (2.96), World Wide Web (2.80) and e-books (2.76, 3.12), books (3.61) and e-books (3.35) were the major resources that enhanced postgraduate students' research activities, according to the respondents. Also, reference (2.85) and Wi-Fi services (2.75) Wi-Fi services (3.17), referral services (3.16) and user education (3.10) were library services that promote postgraduate students' research activities. Findings further revealed that books (2.72), e-journals (2.68), print journals (2.65) internet (2.61), reference services (2.65) and reprographic services (2.37) were the most influential library services among postgraduate students. Both the present and previous studies share key similarities, including a survey research design, the use of structured questionnaires, and descriptive statistical analysis to examine the impact of library resources on academic or research activities. Both studies target postgraduate students, with the present study focusing on those in Benue State, Nigeria, and the previous study on postgraduate students in federal universities in southwest Nigeria. The studies differ in several ways, such as the focus of the research—academic performance in the present study and research activities in the previous study. The present study covers three universities in Benue State, with a larger sample of 368 postgraduate students, whereas the previous study involved 378 respondents from multiple federal universities. Additionally, the present study emphasises library resources, such as books, journals, and services, in relation to academic success, whereas the previous study focuses on research resources, such as e-books, Wi-Fi, and user education. The present study also uses a Taro Yamane formula for sample size, whereas the previous study employed a multi-stage sampling procedure. The present study fills gaps left by the previous one, particularly by exploring the broader influence of library resources on academic performance rather than just on research activities, and by providing insights from a larger, more geographically diverse sample. This allows the present study to contribute new perspectives on how library resources support postgraduate academic success across different regions in Nigeria.

Research Methodology

The study adopted a descriptive survey design, which Creswell and Creswell (2018) note is suitable for systematically collecting data from a defined population through structured questions. The research was conducted in Benue State, Nigeria, a region with 23 local government areas, three major universities (Joseph Sarwuan Tarka University, Benue State University, and University of Mkar), and functional academic libraries that support postgraduate research activities. The population comprised 9,200 registered postgraduate library users across these universities. A sample of 383 respondents was determined using Taro Yamane's formula and selected through multi-stage sampling: proportionate stratified random sampling followed by accidental sampling to ensure accessibility. Data were collected using a structured questionnaire (PIULIRAPP) divided into sections assessing the availability, awareness, utilisation, perceived influence, and challenges of library resources. The instrument was validated by three experts and reliability tested using Cronbach's alpha, yielding coefficients ranging from 0.74 to 0.79, indicating strong internal consistency. Questionnaires were personally distributed and retrieved, achieving a 96.1% return rate (368 valid responses). Data analysis employed descriptive statistics (frequency counts, percentages, means, standard deviations) for research questions, and chi-square tests at a 0.05 significance

level for hypotheses, with defined benchmarks for decision-making on response scales. This methodology ensured a comprehensive, reliable, and systematic examination of the perceived influence of library information resource utilisation on postgraduate academic performance in Benue State.

Result and Discussion

This section deals with the presentation of data, analysis, interpretation and discussion of findings. The presentation follows the sequence of the research questions answered and the null hypotheses that guided the study.

Table 1: Size Distribution and Return Rate

S/N	Institution	Population	Sample Size	Return Frequency	Return %
1	Joseph Sarwuan Tarka University, Makurdi	4,222	176	169	96.02%
2	Benue State University	4,008	167	160	95.81%
3	University of Mkar, Mkar	970	40	39	97.50%
Total		9,200	383	368	96.08%

Table 1 presents the sample size allocation and corresponding response rates across three universities under study in Benue State, Nigeria. The sampling framework employed proportional allocation, ensuring that each institution's sample size was proportional to its total student population of 9,200. A total of 383 questionnaires were administered, of which 368 were duly retrieved, yielding an overall response rate of 96.08%; a figure that significantly exceeds the conventional threshold for acceptable survey response rates in social science research.

Table 2: Mean and standard deviation of respondents on the extent to which postgraduate students utilise library information resources

S/N	Item Statement	VHE	HE	LE	VLE	\bar{x}	SD	Remark
1	Online Databases (e.g., JSTOR, Science Direct, ProQuest)	68	126	130	44	2.59	0.92	HE
2	E-books	13	106	168	81	2.14	0.80	LE
3	Theses and Dissertations	52	123	104	89	2.37	1.00	LE
4	Reference Books (Encyclopedias, Dictionaries)	38	115	145	70	2.33	0.90	LE
5	Research Journals (Print and Electronic)	126	144	77	21	3.02	0.88	HE
Cluster Mean						2.49	0.90	LE

Key: \bar{x} = mean, SD = Standard Deviation, HE = High Extent, LE = Low Extent, Dec. = Decision.

Analysis of Table 2 shows that postgraduate students in Benue State make the greatest use of research journals and online databases, whereas resources such as e-books, theses, and reference books are accessed

less frequently. This pattern suggests that students prioritise sources that directly support their research needs and academic writing (Ajiboye et al., 2023; Arumuru & David, 2024). The cluster mean of 2.49 indicates low-to-moderate utilisation of library resources, signalling potential gaps in awareness, accessibility, or training regarding the full range of available materials (Effiom et al., 2023). These findings align with Olajide and Adio (2017), who observed that underutilisation of certain library materials can limit research efficiency and academic performance.

Table 3: Mean and standard deviation of respondents on the perceived influence of utilisation of library information resources on the academic performance of postgraduate students

S/N	Item Statement	VHI	HI	LI	VLI	\bar{x}	SD	Remark
1	Improved access to relevant academic materials	176	174	18	0	3.43	0.59	HI
2	Support in academic writing	150	197	21	0	3.35	0.59	HI
3	Enhances time management	161	182	25	0	3.37	0.61	HI
4	Improves critical thinking	174	172	22	0	3.41	0.60	HI
5	Enhances presentation skills using multimedia resources	154	190	24	0	3.35	0.60	HI
Cluster Mean						3.38	0.60	HI

Key: \bar{x} = mean, SD = Standard Deviation, HI = High Influence, LI = Low Influence, Dec. = Decision.

Table 3 shows that postgraduate students perceive library resources as having a strong positive impact on their academic performance. Access to relevant materials, guidance on writing, improved time management, critical thinking, and multimedia support were all rated highly. The cluster mean of 3.38 indicates that, overall, library use significantly contributes to students' research efficiency and learning outcomes (Ajiboye et al., 2023; Arumuru & David, 2024). These findings corroborate prior research by Effiom et al. (2023), which highlights the critical role of library resources in supporting postgraduate research and academic excellence.

Table 4: Mean and standard deviation of respondents on the challenges faced by postgraduate students in utilising library information resources

S/N	Item Statement	SA	A	D	SD	\bar{x}	SD	Remark
1	Limited access to digital resources	203	155	10	0	3.52	0.55	SA
2	Inadequate internet connectivity	182	177	9	0	3.47	0.55	A
3	Insufficient training on resource usage	185	170	13	0	3.47	0.57	A
4	Lack of up-to-date materials	170	177	21	0	3.40	0.60	A
5	Inadequate library infrastructure	174	165	29	0	3.39	0.63	A
Cluster Mean						3.45	0.58	A

Key: \bar{x} = mean, SD = Standard Deviation, SA = Strongly Agree, A = Agree, Dec. = Decision.

Table 4 shows that limited digital access is the most pressing challenge, with inadequate internet connectivity and insufficient training also significantly affecting utilisation. The cluster mean of 3.45 indicates that postgraduate students face multiple moderate-to-high challenges in accessing and using

library resources. These results align with previous findings that infrastructure, access, and training deficiencies hinder effective library use and can negatively affect research productivity and academic success (Olajide & Adio, 2017; Effiom et al., 2023).

Conclusion

The findings of this study demonstrate that library information resources in universities in Benue State play a pivotal role in shaping the academic performance of postgraduate students. Although a range of physical and digital resources is available, postgraduate students use them to varying degrees, with research journals and online databases the most frequently accessed. The perceived influence of these resources on academic performance is strong, particularly in areas such as access to relevant materials, enhancement of critical thinking, support for academic writing, time management, and effective presentation skills. Despite these benefits, challenges such as limited digital access, inadequate internet connectivity, insufficient user training, outdated materials, and constrained library infrastructure continue to impede optimal resource utilisation. Overall, the study underscores the importance of effective engagement with library resources for improving postgraduate research quality, promoting independent learning, and enhancing scholarly productivity in Benue State universities.

Recommendations

The following recommendations were made according to the findings of the study:

1. Enhance Digital Infrastructure: Universities should prioritise upgrading internet connectivity, providing reliable Wi-Fi, and ensuring seamless access to online databases and e-resources to reduce digital barriers affecting postgraduate students.
2. Expand Awareness and Training Programs: Academic libraries should conduct regular workshops, orientations, and personalised training sessions to equip postgraduate students with the skills to effectively locate, evaluate, and use both print and electronic resources.
3. Improve Resource Availability: Universities should regularly acquire current textbooks, journals, theses, and electronic materials relevant to postgraduate research areas, ensuring that collections remain comprehensive, up-to-date, and aligned with students' academic needs.
4. Strengthen Library Infrastructure: Adequate physical spaces, modern study environments, and functional facilities should be provided to support independent and collaborative learning, while also integrating technological tools that facilitate efficient utilisation of library resources.

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